

USE OF ALTERNATIVE ENERGY SOURCES IN SOLVING ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

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Abstract. *The Republic of Azerbaijan is a country with rich natural resources and a developed industry. However, due to the untimely resolution of ecological problems accumulated over the years, the environment in the country has been seriously polluted. Currently, the republic faces a number of urgent problems that require resolution, such as the pollution of water basins, including the Caspian Sea, with domestic and industrial waste, damages resulting from changes in the Caspian Sea level, excessive release of harmful gases into the atmosphere, reduction of biological diversity, soil erosion and salinization, and the management of industrial and domestic waste. In recent years, significant achievements have been made in the field of social and economic development in the Republic of Azerbaijan, and ensuring the sustainability of these achievements has been accepted as the country's main priority. The country's environmental strategy is implemented through the protection of natural resources, the sustainable use of economic and human resources, the strengthening of coordination of environmental protection activities, and the application of science-based development principles. This strategy aims to secure the interests of present and future generations. The use of alternative energy sources plays a crucial role in solving environmental problems and ensuring energy security. These energy sources reduce fuel consumption, increase energy efficiency, prevent the depletion of non-renewable resources, and contribute to environmental protection. At the same time, they reduce the dependence of the country's economic systems on oil and gas prices and create opportunities for improving social well-being through the implementation of new technologies. In summary, the application of alternative energy sources makes a significant contribution to both the reduction of ecological problems and the sustainability of economic and social development. Increasing the use of renewable energy sources and implementing relevant state programs in Azerbaijan is of strategic importance for ensuring both the country's ecological and energy security.*

Keywords: *alternative, climate change, environmental policy*

INTRODUCTION

В по After gaining independence, the Republic of Azerbaijan initiated deep transformation processes in the social, economic, and political spheres. These changes also impacted the field of environmental protection, leading to a new phase in environmental policy [1,2]. During the period of independence, the assessment of environmental issues not only as a national problem but also as part of global ecological challenges allowed for the formation of the basic approaches to environmental protection in our country.

Azerbaijan's rich natural resources—oil, gas, land, and water resources—are of strategic importance for the country's economic development. However, as a result of rapid industrialization, urbanization, and population growth, the ecological balance has been disturbed, and an intensification of anthropogenic impact has been observed in many regions. Consequently, serious ecological problems have arisen, such as the pollution of water basins, changes in the Caspian Sea level, soil erosion and salinization, air pollution with harmful gases, reduction of forest cover, and limitation of biological diversity [2,3].

One of the first documents prepared after independence was the "Ecological Concept of the Republic of Azerbaijan." This document, based on the principles of "Sustainable Development," determined the main directions for environmental protection and the efficient use of natural resources [2,3]. The concept notes that the main goal of environmental policy is to ensure the needs of present and future generations through the protection of existing ecological systems and the efficient use of economic potential and natural resources [4].

Currently, Azerbaijan has identified several key priorities in the field of environmental protection:

- Ensuring ecological security – application of advanced technologies to minimize pollution and ensure the sustainable protection of the environment [5];
- Development of alternative and renewable energy sources – utilizing inexhaustible energy sources and increasing energy efficiency, and efficient management of natural resources [6];
- National and international cooperation – evaluation of national needs and application of international experience in solving global ecological problems [1,3].

The achievements Azerbaijan has made in this direction in recent years have strengthened the country's energy security, contributed to environmental protection, and enhanced economic stability. In particular, the use of alternative energy sources—solar, wind, and small river hydroelectric power stations—has allowed for the formation of an ecologically clean energy model in the region [6,7].

Moreover, ecological policy has become an essential component of sustainable development strategies not only in the energy sector but also in areas such as industry, agriculture, transport, urban planning, and tourism [5]. This approach serves to reconcile ecological and economic interests, as well as ensure a healthy and balanced ecosystem for future generations.

Thus, since independence, the Republic of Azerbaijan has prioritized the sustainable development model by benefiting from both national and international experience in the development of environmental policy. This has created a strong foundation for the wide application of alternative energy sources, increased energy efficiency, and the development of ecologically clean technologies in the country [1,6].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In recent years, countries around the world have been trying to incorporate new and clean energy sources into their fuel and energy balance. Azerbaijan has also joined this trend and started to expand the use of alternative and renewable energy sources [6,7].

Among non-conventional energy sources, wind, solar, wave, small river hydrology energy, biomass, and geothermal energy are of particular importance. The potential of these energy sources is significant, and they are considered ecologically clean [6].

1. Analysis of Alternative Energy Sources

The economic and ecological importance of alternative energy sources manifests itself in several directions:

- **Reduction of fuel consumption:** By integrating these energy sources into the economic cycle, the use of organic fuel resources (oil, gas, peat, coal, wood, etc.) is reduced, and energy is saved [6,7].
- **Ecological benefit:** Use results in a decrease in the release of harmful wastes into the environment, and the pollution of air, water, and soil is minimized [6,7].
- **Energy security:** The use of alternative energy sources reduces the country's dependence on energy resources and minimizes dependence on energy prices [7].
- **Socio-economic impact:** New energy projects generate additional income for the population, create jobs, and stimulate regional economic development [5,7].

2. Applied Methods

The following methods and approaches are applied in the Republic of Azerbaijan for the use of alternative energy sources and environmental protection:

- **Wind energy:** Installation of wind power plants in flat and open areas, integration of energy into the grid, and optimization of energy efficiency [6].

- **Solar energy:** Use of solar batteries in tropical and subtropical latitudes, integration of photovoltaic systems, and application of water heaters [6].

- **Biomass energy:** Energy production from wood, wood chips, and other biological waste in regions rich in forest resources, application of special combustion technologies [6,7].

- **Hydropower:** Regional electricity production utilizing the hydrological potential of small rivers and water basins [7].

- **Geothermal energy:** Exploiting the potential of underground thermal waters and volcanic areas to produce thermal and electrical energy [7].

- **Assessment of global environmental problems:** Analysis of ecological risks at the national and regional level, monitoring of waste and pollution, development of environmental protection standards [1,3].

3. Approaches in Environmental Protection

- **Application of sustainable development principles:** Ensuring the unity of efficient use of natural resources, protection of ecological systems, and economic development [2,4].

- **Stimulation of alternative energy projects:** Promotion of energy projects through state programs, tax incentives, and investment promotion [5,6].

- **International cooperation:** Implementation of global ecological standards, studying international experience, and adapting it to the conditions of Azerbaijan [1,3].

On the one hand, the methods in the field of using alternative energy sources and environmental protection in the Republic of Azerbaijan are based on a systematic approach, both technologically, economically, and ecologically. These methods increase energy efficiency, reduce waste, and ensure sustainable development for future generations [6,7].

On the other hand, one of the questions that worries the world community in the modern era—"how to meet the growing energy demands of humanity"—is answered optimistically [6]. Alternative energy is not only vital for environmental protection. It reduces the dependence of countries, territories, and economic systems on oil and its price [9].

Due to regional characteristics, the structure of alternative energy use shows the superiority of certain sources. The use of wind power plants in flat areas and solar batteries in tropical and subtropical latitudes is appropriate [6]. Biomass (wood, wood chips) with special combustion technology is widely used in countries rich in forest resources [6,7].

Non-conventional (alternative) renewable energy sources include [6,7]:

- Biomass energy
- Wind energy
- Solar energy
- Hydropower
- Geothermal energy
- Wave energy
- Nuclear fission energy
- Thermonuclear fusion energy
- Hydrogen fuel energy
- Tidal and ebb energy
- Ocean thermal energy

The use of these natural energy carriers, which have been widely utilized in various regions of Europe in recent decades, is now a focus of attention in Azerbaijan [2,6]. The use of alternative energy sources in our country will reduce fuel consumption in thermal power plants, bring additional income to the population, and positively affect the quality of living conditions [5,7].

RESULTS

The measures implemented in the Republic of Azerbaijan for the development of alternative energy sources and environmental protection increase the country's energy security, improve the ecological situation, and ensure economic diversification.

The involvement and efficient use of the country's natural and economic resources in the economic cycle are being increased for the development of the non-oil sector. Stimulating measures, strengthening of scientific and technical potential, and specialist training are being continued to accelerate the use of alternative energy sources. The participation of the private sector in this process is encouraged, and flexible regulation of alternative energy tariffs is ensured.

Consequently, the application of alternative energy sources serves to ensure sustainable development not only in the energy and economic fields but also in the ecological and social spheres. This allows the Republic of Azerbaijan to gain a strategic advantage in environmental and energy policy at both national and international levels.

A network of production, social, and market infrastructure that meets modern requirements will be created, serving the development of the non-oil sector, and the application of modern management and economic methods will be expanded.

DISCUSSION

Energy security and environmental protection are of great importance for the Republic of Azerbaijan, both in a national and global perspective. Global climate change, pollution of the atmosphere and water basins, and the reduction of biological diversity are major challenges for humanity and developed regions in the modern era. The use of alternative and renewable energy sources is considered a strategic priority in solving these problems.

The application of alternative energy sources affects several important directions:

- **Environmental protection:** The ecological cleanliness of the energy sources used and the reduction of waste improve the state of the environment.

- **Reduction of dependence on energy resources:** Alternative energy sources minimize dependence on finite resources such as oil and gas and increase the country's energy security.

- **Economic impact:** New energy projects generate additional income for the population, create jobs, and stimulate regional development.

Azerbaijan's energy policy, focusing on the use of alternative and renewable energy sources, covers not only the energy sector but also agriculture, industry, urban planning, and tourism. This approach serves to ensure sustainable development and ecological balance in the country.

For example, the "Ecological Park" project implemented in the Caspian region included extensive landscaping works across 9.3 hectares, the mass planting of trees and shrubs, and the ecological awareness-raising of the younger generation. This project positively affects both ecological cleanliness and the quality of life of the population. Furthermore, thanks to the programs and incentive measures implemented by the state, energy efficiency in the non-oil sector is increased, and the use of alternative energy sources is expanded.

Global experience shows that the systematic use of alternative energy sources meets energy demand, reduces ecological risks, and ensures economic diversification. Azerbaijan is actively implementing measures to diversify its energy balance and ensure environmental protection by adapting this experience to national conditions.

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